

Enterprise Culture: Literature Review

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Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to review research on corporate culture, thereby giving theories about corporate culture and typical corporate culture forms in Vietnam. Based on the theoretical basis of corporate culture, the author conducts an analysis of the current state of corporate culture at the Vietnam Dairy Products Corporation - Vinamilk. Finally, the author gives recommendations to enhance the value and role of corporate culture in Vietnamese enterprises.

Keywords: Enterprise culture, vinamilk, Vietnam.

1. Introduction

In the context of increasingly deepening economic integration, the competitive advantage of enterprises is no longer just products, revenue, brands ... but the first and most core is Corporate Culture. Your competitors can copy everything from strategies, products, systems, processes to know-how, technology ... but only one thing they cannot copy or steal. That is the culture of the business.

CORPORATE CULTURE determines the longevity of an enterprise. "It helps businesses outlast the founders' lives." Many people believe that ENTERPRISE CULTURE is an asset of an enterprise. Culture makes up the personality of the enterprise, on the contrary, the enterprise is known through its culture.

Most small and medium enterprises in Vietnam have not really focused on corporate culture - factors for connection and human development, because businesses do not understand the influence, importance as well as how to build corporate culture.

2. Literature review

2.1. Culture

Culture is an existing and developing field associated with human life, is a unique characteristic of human, there are many different definitions of culture in the world. In 1952, Kroeber and Kluckolm collected 164 different cultural definitions. Until now, the number of definitions has probably continued to increase. The first widely accepted definition of culture in the world was the one given by anthropologist EB Tylor: "culture is a complex whole consisting of knowledge, beliefs, art, morality, , laws, customs and all the skills and habits that people gain as a member of a society. And Edward Hall understands culture as "A system for creating, transferring, storing. and information processing. The thread that crosses all cultures is communication and communication". Culture is understood as culture in a broad sense, encompassing all that man has created and culture is an identity of each individual, every nation, and every nation that no one can easily forget.

According to UNESCO, there is another definition of culture: "Culture reflects and expresses in a general and vivid way every aspect of life (of each individual and of each community) that took place in the past, also As happening in the present, over the centuries it has formed a system of values, traditions, aesthetics and lifestyles and based on which each nation asserts its own identity ". Thus culture means a long tradition.

According to President Ho Chi Minh: "Culture is the synthesis of all modes of living with all its manifestations, human beings are born to adapt to the needs of life and the demands of survival".

Culture includes everything, is a part of human life, culture is not only about the spirit but includes all matter. In addition to non-material factors such as values, standards, culture also includes tangible human creations such as temples, historic sites ...

Sociologists divide culture into two forms: individual culture and community culture. Individual culture is the whole capital of knowledge and experience accumulated into each individual, manifested in that individual's system of concepts and behavior in practical life. Community culture is the culture of a social group, it is not a simple plus number of individual culture - members of that social community. In business activities, "business culture" is in the form of individual culture, and "corporate culture" is in the form of community culture.

Culture is a means for people to "adjust" (improve) their life towards the direction of reaching true, good and beautiful values. Considered as the "foundation", "both the goal and the driving force for the development" of people and the society is more and more balanced and sustainable, culture has a positive effect on development. of each individual as well as the entire community. The internal strength of a nation is first of all, all resources gathered from traditional cultural capital accumulated in its own history.

Thus, in essence, culture is a system of values produced in a certain society, characterized by certain socio-economic forms, including both material and spiritual values.

Culture is not a non-economic factor, on the contrary, culture and business are closely intertwined: culture and business have a common goal of serving people, culture is a great resource for business, but the short-term goals of culture and business can be contradictory, if the business is only chasing immediate profits, it will harm culture, erode national cultural identity, when the culture carries inappropriate elements, it will hinder and hinder the development of business.

2.2. Corporate culture

In an enterprise, especially large-scale businesses, is a collection of people with different qualifications, cultural background, cognitive level, social relations, geographic region, cultural ideology, ... it is this difference that creates a diverse and complex working environment even with conflicting things. In addition, with the increasingly fierce competition of the market economy and the trend of globalization, forcing businesses to survive and develop must continually explore new, creative and changing things. in accordance with reality. How to make the business a gathering place, promoting all human resources, a place to make a hyphen, a place that can create a regulatory force, impact (positive or negative) for all factors Different subjective and objective factors, increasing the value of each individual human resource many times in order to contribute to the sustainable development of the enterprise. This requires the enterprise to build and maintain a specific culture that promotes competencies and promotes the contribution of all employees to the achievement of the overall goals of the organization. Therefore, corporate culture can be affirmed as an intangible asset of each enterprise.

CORPORATE CULTURE can be understood as all cultural values that are created during the existence and development of an enterprise, becoming the values, conceptions and customs, eating traditions. deep into the operation of that business and dominate the emotions, thinking and behavior of all members of the business in the pursuit and realization of common goals. Marvin Bower - General Manager, McKinsey Co. said "ENTERPRISE CULTURE are all elements that we are implementing in the business process and the legacy is left to the next generation."

And the American sociologist ENSchein gave the definition of CORPORATE CULTURE as follows: "Corporate culture is the sum of methods and rules to solve problems of external adaptation and internal unity within employees. , rules have been effective in the past and are still imperative in the present. These rules and tactics are the starting factor in employees choosing how to act, analyze and make decisions. Members of the corporate organization do not think twice about the meaning of those rules and procedures, but consider them right from the start.

As such, the content of corporate culture is not something randomly generated by itself, it is formed in the process of real business operations, in the process of communication, interaction and interaction. relationship, as a solution to problems that the internal and external environments pose to the business. Corporate culture shows the needs, purposes and business direction of the business.

N.Demetr - the French sociologist also said that corporate culture - it is a system of concepts, symbols, values, and behavioral stereotypes that all members of the enterprise. perceive and follow. That means in the enterprise all members are sticking together by common criteria in business activities. The main function of ENTERPRISE CULTURE is to create the unity of all members, in the enterprise. In addition, CORPORATE CULTURE also ensures the harmony between collective interests with individual interests and helps each individual perform their role in accordance with the general direction of the business. In general, CORPORATE CULTURE motivates the energy and will of members of the enterprise and directs that spirit to strive for the purpose of the enterprise. CORPORATE CULTURE also contributes to the difference between businesses and is considered a tradition of each enterprise.

2.3. Behavioral culture in enterprises

Behavioral culture in the business is part of ENTERPRISE CULTURE. Internal relationships within enterprises are built and maintained, and sustainably developed will create close links throughout the enterprise and this is a great internal resource of each enterprise. Besides, the working environment is becoming more and more diverse, so it is required that a behavioral culture be established sustainably. However, many Vietnamese businesses today have never focused on building and strengthening the behavioral culture in their businesses. Therefore, internal conflicts and conflicts occur consecutively, employees quit their jobs ... In order to build a business and a sustainable corporate culture, each enterprise needs to build a code of conduct. internally consistent with the own CORPORATE CULTURE.

Behavioral culture in enterprises is the behavioral relationship between superiors and subordinates, between colleagues, between people and work, built on the common values of the enterprise. Each enterprise has its own behavioral culture, with its own characteristics, consistent with the behavioral culture of the community. The development of enterprises must be associated with building and strengthening internal relationships within enterprises. Only then will businesses have sustainable development.

Behavioral culture in enterprises plays an important role, is one of the factors that contribute to building corporate image, building corporate culture with its own identity. Building corporate image: Behavior between superiors and subordinates, between colleagues has a great influence on work efficiency, to the success of enterprises. Behavior in enterprises is responded by everyone in the enterprise, will promote working spirit, promote democracy, develop individual abilities of all members. Both businesses will stick together in the spirit of cooperation, development, and contribution to common goals. That cohesion creates the strength to move businesses forward. Building ENTERPRISE CULTURE with its own identity: Behavioral culture is part of ENTERPRISE CULTURE. Building and strengthening relationships in businesses is the way to build and develop ENTERPRISE CULTURE.

The leaders' conduct principles to subordinates: As the head of the business, the leader plays a very important role in the process of building a culture of behavior in the business. They have to know how to recruit, use the right job, the right place, offer fair reward and punishment, know how to recruit employees, listen to, receive feedback from employees, know how to resolve conflicts and conflicts. effective intrinsic punching. When implementing these principles, the leader will build a culture of good behavior in the business

Recruiting, using the right people for the right job, in the right place: When the leader selects the right people and uses the right people, the right job will promote employees' potential, giving employees passion for work.

Fair reward and punishment regime: When performing the management work, leaders must be reprimanded, rewarded and must be conducted fairly. When reprimanding, the leader must be based on the interests of the collective and the enterprise. Reprimand also requires art, so that the staff happily accept and strive to do better. When employees do well, reward them in front of the group.

Conquering subordinate employees: Leaders are not merely giving orders, orders and then enforcing employees. The leader must have art, understanding human psychology in order to win employees who voluntarily follow him. Assigning the work to employees, but the leader must also have the same enthusiastic attitude as I start working.

Be mindful of employee feedback: Employee feedback is like customer feedback, so the leader should consider the employee's feedback.

Resolve internal conflicts and conflicts effectively: First of all, help employees resolve their own conflicts. When conflicts, conflicts arise, leaders must know how to find a way to solve them so that they do not affect the general work, and all stakeholders are satisfied.

Code of conduct of subordinates with leaders. Successful leaders are the ones who empower and create the best conditions for their subordinates to manage their superiors, creating understanding between the two sides. To achieve this, the subordinates' behavior towards the leader must be built on specific principles: subordinates must show their role, must become an effective supporter of the leader. The subordinates must perform their roles: First of all, employees must complete the assigned tasks with the highest sense of responsibility. They also have to boldly challenge new and challenging jobs to prove their ability to the leader. That endeavor is not only for the business, for the boss, but first of all for himself. When performing their role, each employee will increase their personal values. Enterprise will link individual values together in the common value of the business. The subordinates must become the leader's powerful supporter: Not only do their duties perfectly, but each employee becomes effective supporters and advisers to their superiors. me. Come up with an idea and convince the leader to approve your idea. Of course in order to do that, employees must understand what the leader wants.

Some principles of conduct among colleagues. To build a behavioral culture in a sustainable enterprise, all members must build a colleague relationship, build an open, cooperative attitude with each other. No matter how strong each individual is, it is difficult to succeed without cooperating and helping each other. Solid colleague relationships, will create the strength of the business. Building a colleague relationship: Administrators believe that how to use people, what is important in the conduct of leaders, is a direct factor creating the relationship. interpersonal relationships in the business. Therefore, building co-worker relationships must be based on cooperation, promoting together towards a common goal. Building an open, cooperative attitude with each other: Being active, capable of independent thinking, experienced ... is not enough to create a professional working style. All members of the business must have an open spirit and cooperate with colleagues. The harmonious coordination will create the highest work efficiency.

Code of conduct for work: Whether you are a leader or an employee, your behavior towards your job is to respect your work. Only then can you be productive and have fun at work. Show respect for work with a sense of responsibility for the job. Take responsibility when you make mistakes, by working harder, making sure that mistakes don't happen again. Perform the assigned work on schedule, schedule, with the highest creativity and effort, to achieve the highest results. But you should not stop at the assigned job, but always explore and discover your ability in new areas. The attitude of respect to work is reflected in every aspect: respect for working hours, not wasting time working at the company on personal things, or complying with the working regulations of the company. ty ...

2.4. The role of corporate culture:

CORPORATE CULTURE has a very important position and role in the development of every business.

* For the outside:

- Make a difference with other businesses.
- Create attractive talent.
- Create partner's trust.
- Create image and brand of the business.
- Create community trust.
- Protect your business from outside attacks.

* For inside:

- Create solidarity and stickiness within the business.
- Build good traditions.
- Discovering hidden talents through cultural activities.
- Build employees' pride in their company.

Culture is created as a mechanism to assert the goals of the enterprise, to guide and shape the behavior and behavior of the members of the enterprise. Any organization also has some hidden insights, invisible principles affecting daily behavior at work ... It is evident when new members join the organization, immediately. from the beginning they are not accepted as former members, they have to learn these intangible principles of managers, or former employees, they have to learn the principles of the organization. Violation of these intangible principles by managers, or enforcement officers, will lead to results that are difficult to be accepted by everyone and even result in results that are difficult to be accepted by everyone and even be removed from organization. The observance of these principles serves as the first bases for reward and promotion. Appropriate people, or have a strong influence on the organization as well as its members, means that they must be the ones whose behavior and behavior are culturally appropriate. It's not a coincidence that all Disney Park employees look so attractive, clean, and smiling. That is exactly the image that Disney wants to give everyone. That culture is embodied with laws and orthodox principles to ensure that all Disney employees act consistently and adhere to those images.

Although the impact of ENTERPRISE CULTURE on corporate performance has both polarity and hindering factors, many of its functions are valuable to the business as well as its members. Culture encourages commitment in a business, consistency in the behavior of its members. This is clearly beneficial for a business. Culture is also valuable to the members of the business, because it reduces their ambiguity, it tells them how things should be done and what is important.

The role of corporate culture in management activities

Administration is the synthesis of activities that are done to ensure work is done through the efforts of others. In other words, governance is how to get those under them to perform their jobs most effectively to achieve common goals. If you want to run (dictate) employees, managers need to master a system of meanings, values, beliefs of owners, perceptions and methods of thinking that are agreed upon by them, affecting how their behavior (the corporate culture). So ENTERPRISE CULTURE is the tool and means through which the manager performs his or her managerial work. But CORPORATE CULTURE also has certain influences on the decisions of managers as well as shaping their leadership style. For companies with a cultural identity that do not focus on building trust with employees, managers often resort to centralized, authoritarian measures, instead

of decentralized and democratic measures. Once there is a ENTERPRISE CULTURE, the management pressure of the leadership will be reduced thanks to the sharing of subordinates. Employees will have the right to know how to operate and what to do in difficult situations. In an organizational environment where everyone is involved, it is true that the role of directors in cultural management and cultural management.

CORPORATE CULTURE affects the general governance and thus all activities under the management functions: strategic management, human resource management, production administration, financial management, Marketing ...

Each organization must develop strategic plans to develop its roadmap and action plan to move forward and fulfill its mission (overall goal) in a volatile business environment. As it is today, it is strategic management, whose product is the business strategy of the enterprise. Indeed, a business strategy helps a company to adapt and capture target market opportunities within its existing and potential capabilities and resources in the context of fluctuating foreign factors. . An organization with a strong culture will increase the determination of its members, striving for the common value and strategy of the business. On the contrary, a “weak” culture leads to a decrease in employee ambiguity, determination and enthusiasm, conflict, chaos, disorientation. Furthermore, in order to draft a strategy (a decision chain that drives development and makes a qualitative change within the business), information needs to be collected. The way in which information about the operating environment is collected has a great influence on strategic direction. When collecting information and analyzing the business environment, the surveyors and analysts are based on assumptions or models, and certain screening methods make the collected material partially lose the reality. , objectivity and comprehensiveness. The collected documents are expressed in ways and languages prevailing in the organization, they are influenced by organizational cultural characteristics. It can be affirmed that ENTERPRISE CULTURE is always reflected in the business strategy, and the business strategy is also a great plan, "general activity program" to implement corporate culture. CORPORATE CULTURE is a tool that unifies people about awareness, awareness and action in the process of implementing action programs. In fact, CORPORATE CULTURE is an important contributor (or hindrance) to successful strategy implementation. Thomas Watson.Jr, a successful IBM CEO, said: “The philosophy, spirit and desire of an organization have a much greater impact on the company's achievements than the source. Technical, economic, organizational structure, initiative, and adjustment of all of these resources have a strong contribution to the success of the company. But in my opinion, they are performed exceptionally well by everyone in the organization who firmly believes in the fundamental principles and values of the company and proceeds with unwavering loyalty. Beliefs, goals and practices set out in a strategy may or may not be relevant to ENTERPRISE CULTURE. When they don't get along, a company often has difficulty implementing that strategy successfully. A culturally consistent strategy motivates everyone in the company to do their job in the context of all that bolstering the strategy, greatly increasing the power and efficiency of the execution. comb. A strong cultural environment promotes long-term business and production activities when it is compatible with the strategy and will significantly harm the achievement of the company when it is less appropriate. When company culture does not fit what is necessary for the success of the strategy, the culture is changed most quickly. The more firmly established a culture is, the more difficult it is to implement a new or different strategy. The grand and long-lasting conflict between strategy and culture will weaken, and possibly even fail, every effort in implementing the strategy.

A cultural-strategic coherence is a powerful lever for creating consistent behavior and helping employees work in a better strategic way. At that time, businesses will create a system of unorthodox principles and pressure to conduct internal work and let each person know how to perform their duties. Behavior acceptable to the corporate culture environment thrives, while unacceptable behaviors are eliminated and punished. In a company, where culture and strategy are false, ingrained, and operating philosophies do not develop work habits that encourage strategy: often there are many types of behaviors to conduct. strategy to be successful and attract negative acknowledgment rather than judgment and reward. In addition, this bond nurtures and motivates people to do their best: it provides the structure, standards and value systems in which it

operates; and it strongly promotes the corporate image among the employees of the company. All of this makes employees feel better and more authentic about their working environment, stimulating them to work closer and closer to their best potential.

Human resource management is all activities of an organization to attract, build, develop, use, evaluate, preserve and maintain a workforce in accordance with the organization's work requirements. In terms of quantity and quality. Therefore, human resource management is also deeply influenced by corporate culture, the psychosocial atmosphere in the business, lifestyles, and the need to perceive human values in the enterprise. Influence the way of thinking and human resource management policies of organizations. Moreover, the implementation of human resource management is also to exploit the potentials of physical strength and more importantly human intellect to suit the work requirements of that organization is also a tool. Building corporate culture, specific activities of human resource management: recruiting, selecting, maintaining, developing, using, motivating and providing facilities for human resources in the organization is also the picture. Expressions of that corporate culture. When a strong culture has been formed in the enterprise, the employees will devote their best to the enterprise's goals, the corporate culture will be the end to steer employees in the direction of working without thinking only of money. Bonuses and administrators probably won't need to resort to a lot of monetary incentives.

Production management is the management of the process or system that creates goods and services. CORPORATE CULTURE also has a profound influence on this sector, it acts as a catalyst that unites employees, creates a strong mental motivation in the workforce, helps production managers achieve (reduce costs to the lowest possible level to achieve the highest profit, shorten production time, organize the construction of production and service delivery systems with high flexibility to adapt to change change to improve competitiveness: quality, design, price ...)

Quality culture is also a part of ENTERPRISE CULTURE. Quality management is essentially the process of building a quality culture in an enterprise. Therefore, in order to fulfill their duties, a quality manager cannot help but pay attention to his corporate culture.

Even in the field of financial management, corporate reputation for the state, credit institutions, shareholders, transparency and honesty of information about the financial status of the business, is also reflect the height of that corporate culture. A business with a unique cultural identity is an enterprise that creates trust among shareholders and investors, then the work belongs to the financial management function (raising capital, increasing efficiency of capital use, increase the market value of the business ...) is also relieved of pressure.

CORPORATE CULTURE also determines product designs, affects product distribution, influences business promotion and support measures, and prices (because the price customers pay for a product. depends on both its perceived value and its real value). Thus, CORPORATE CULTURE also affects the Marketing field of the business.

The role of ENTERPRISE CULTURE in the business performance

CORPORATE CULTURE has a comprehensive impact on business activities:

- * Create a unique identity for that business, to recognize the difference between one business and another, help businesses build their name. That difference is reflected in intangible assets such as: employee loyalty, the atmosphere of the business as a small family, accelerating the process of discussion and decision-making. reason, the trust of employees in the decisions and policies of the business, team spirit in all work of the enterprise ...

- * Conveying the consciousness and values of the business to the members of that enterprise.

* Culture creates a common commitment for the goals and values of the enterprise, it is greater than the interests of each individual in that enterprise. Help to resolve daily conflicts in the process of business operations.

* Culture creates stability in the enterprise: Therefore, it can be said that culture is as a binder among business members, to help manage the business by giving standards to guide the What members should say and do.

Thereby, ENTERPRISE CULTURE performs its roles in the activities of the business:

Culture contributes to reducing conflicts, building blocks of great unity:

Most researchers in culture emphasize the important role of culture in promoting social cohesion in businesses. Culture is described as "glue" or "cement" to connect the members of the business together. Creating a common culture will create a unity of views, views, choices and common interests for the actions of employees. This is very meaningful for businesses that have conflicts and lack of internal consistency. Moreover, in order to survive and respond to the changing environment, the important issues that most businesses have to face are to create a high consistency in the implementation of functions, strategies, set goals of the business.

Coordination and control: in a broader view, culture promotes unity in awareness, is also the enterprise, creating behavioral patterns of that enterprise, accepted and complied by members. internal corporate harmony as a whole, as well as decision-making in particular. Especially in decision-making encountering complex realities, due to the differences in awareness, about local cultures of the members, ENTERPRISE CULTURE will work to scatter choices. . Culture is not only seen as an element that facilitates coordination, but in the form of values, beliefs, behaviors, especially common perceptions. Culture also gives the power to control the business. Cultural opinions have effectively limited the behavior of business members, they are only free to express their personal opinions in the general framework of the business, which in many cases. even stronger than formal corporate principles. Many businesses have tried to rally their culture for a competitive advantage. This is a demonstration of cultural competitiveness to create the desired behavior and ensure the implementation of the principle.

2.5. Content implementation of corporate culture

Before planning to impact on ENTERPRISE CULTURE, it is necessary to determine the type of culture that the business is oriented towards. Each business, company in different industries has different behavior and career style.

The following are some features of a ENTERPRISE CULTURE that is widely used and successfully used in the world. However, it should depend on the characteristics and fields of operation of the enterprise to apply accordingly

- Divide work clearly
- Commitment to work for a long time
- The employee is legally authorized to do the job
- Good relationship between members in the business
- Efficient management systems and processes
- Having clear regulations on reward and discipline
- Highlighting customer orientation
- Focus on recruiting and retaining qualified employees

- Accountability of employees and managers

- Appreciate effort, progress

It is necessary to align corporate culture with long-term goals:

- Promote the strategy of enhancing the current corporate culture and reorganize the parts that are not oriented towards corporate culture.

- Applying the new style of behavior and professional manners to all employees and observe and evaluate the effects of corporate culture on work efficiency.

3. Some typical models of ENTERPRISE CULTURE

3.1. Family culture model

When it comes to family, we immediately think of a familiar, spiritual home. In the model of family business culture, the relationship between members is directly close, but is ranked above and below, like in the family. The family culture model is responsible for providing a working environment like in a home. A typical example of the family model is Japanese firms.

a. Leadership power and relationships among members

The leader is like a "father", rich in experience and has great power over the employees - "the son". The result is a power-driven business, in which the leader acts like a father knowing what to do and knowing what's good for the kids. This is a very friendly, peaceful type of power that is not threatening or pressuring.

With the model of family business culture, satisfaction in family relationships creates motivation, high labor productivity and the ability to resolve conflicts. Job satisfaction from superiors is a reward. Leaders must be an example, have a voice, create their own role model, have a position and want their subordinates to "share the same direction", ... Skillful leaders act as catalysts, creating abundant energy. Abundant, and attractive to the depths of subordinates' love and passion. They are like the leaders of the liberation, reform, protest, enlightenment movements for members and society.

The power in the family culture model is exercised through harmony among the members. The big punishment for the members is not being loved by everyone. The pressure on them is social ethics, not financial or legal. The power in the family model cannot be contested because it does not depend on the task but on the position attributed. The older people will have more power, they must be fully directed and absolutely faithful in order to deserve their status.

ENTERPRISE CULTURE following a family model tends to become a closed environment. The more information available, the richer traditions and customs of the family, the stronger the connection is, the more closed the environment, the more difficult it is for outsiders to become a member.

Many corporations follow a family culture model such as Egypt, Italy, Singapore, North Korea, Spain and typically Japan. The Japanese have built an organized business like a traditional family. Ethics in business is the affection between people of different ranks, younger people are cherished and pampered, and older people are respected. This business ethic also creates more value than any binding contract or contract. Family relations in the business are very long term and dedicated. Japanese companies find ways to provide cheap products to employees, help them find accommodation, help their children go to school, and even sick employees' parents personally come to visit. . Japanese owners believe that the more the company does for the family, the more family wishes to dedicate themselves to the company.

b. Think, learn and change:

Enterprises following the family culture model are more intuitive than knowledge, pay more attention to human development than exploit human capabilities. Personal knowledge is valued higher than personal experience. The person doing it is more important than the work being done.

The change in the political family model will absorb factors that change the policy. What's attracted are new visions, mass appeal, directional goals and, above all, a close relationship with important figures. But the complete reorganization doesn't work like that unless there is a rebellion that poses a great challenge to the leader, in which case franchising could happen.

Training, mentoring, coaching and apprenticeship play an important role in the educational process of a person, but this happens because of the family's mandate, not their own. Family models can respond quickly to changing power influences because of their strong political status.

c. Encourage, reward and resolve conflicts:

Since family members value relationships so much, they can be encouraged with praise or appreciation rather than money. They are not suitable for compensation or any incentives that could threaten the bond with the family.

Conflict resolution is based on the wisdom of the leader. They rarely criticize openly because if they do that the family will fall into chaos. Negative feedback is often in the form of indirect and sometimes in some cases with special "permission".

The family model is less concerned with productivity than efficiency (working the right way).

3.2. Model of Eiffel Tower

The Eiffel Tower of Paris was chosen as the symbol for this cultural model because the tower has a steep, balanced, narrow at the top and widening at the bottom, firmly and firmly. Like a mainstream movement, this is truly a symbol of the mechanical age. Even its structure is more important than function.

a. Leadership, power and relationships among members

A characteristic of the Eiffel Tower model is division of labor towards roles and functions. Each role is distributed in a department, the task will be completed according to the plan. One supervisor can track the performance of a task, a manager can track the work of many supervisors; and so divide it in order.

The hierarchy in the pyramid model is very different from the family model. The higher order is clearly divided, showing the lower order operating function. Employees obey the boss because they have a leading role. An employer has the legal power to command an employee, decide contract terms, impose or simply force an employee to act on his direction. The boss is selected according to the role orientation. If this leader cannot be responsible, there will be a replacement without difference in the duties or the reason for existence of the organization. Performance of work effectively is decisive and the level of work completion will be the basis of performance evaluation.

In this model, little attention is paid to opportunity or individual style. As a result, power comes from the capacity to hold a role. If you meet your boss at the golf course, you don't have to yield to your boss and your boss may not like it either. The hierarchy in the pyramid scheme is very objective, legal based in which everyone complies with company rules and these rules apply to all ranks to increase efficiency as well as oppression.

Each role at each level in the hierarchy is described, ranked by difficulty level, complexity and responsibility, and corresponding salary level. Next is the search for the right person for that position. In the recruitment process, the human resources department will select a fair, objective, based on criteria of working skills,

competencies in accordance with job requirements and thereby assigning jobs appropriately. The process of rating and advancement is similar.

b. Think, learn and change

The way people think, learn and change in pyramid-based companies is different from family-based firms. For pyramidal workers, the family model is autocratic, unreasonable, difficult to understand. Instead of complying with regulatory procedures and objective standards, the family model always changes the key positions or impedes competitiveness.

Learning in the pyramid model is to accumulate the necessary skills, suitable for the role and higher position. For example, you are an employee and want to advance in the position of manager, you must practice the skills, knowledge and competencies enough to undertake the job in that position. For the Eiffel Tower model, people are perceived as capital sources or cash sources. Thanks to a system of skills, qualified and qualified people can plan, deploy, and reform personnel to achieve the goal of exploiting and maximizing the value of human resources. Thus, it can be said that the mission of the human resources department is to trade in human capabilities. All personnel planning, HR assessment, recruitment, training, and job rotation help with sorting and allocating resources to match the identified roles.

Changes in tower model take place through changes in rules and regulations. Along with a change of purpose, a company must go from a change in the requirements placed on its employees. Therefore, the business culture of the Eiffel Tower model is difficult to adapt to the changing environment. Because change is extremely complex and time consuming. Work manuals must be rewritten, changes to policy procedures, regimes, promotion and quality reassessment must be considered. "Improvement" or "rationalization" are the scary terms in the pyramid model.

c. Encourage, reward and resolve conflicts

Workforce model is very strict and strict. They worry when they lack command or direction. Mission is an important concept with role oriented employees.

Conflict is seen as absurdity, boil in disciplinary procedures and an insult to work performance. Complaints and criticisms are handled through a variety of rules and legal procedures to find the truth.

3.3. Pattern of guided missile culture

The goal is a key element of the guided missile model. Everything is done to uphold the strategic intentions and achieve the goals. Everyone knows their work well and their compensation is paid according to the actual results of their contributions.

a. Leadership power and relationships among members

A mission-oriented missile model is undertaken by a team or project team. This differs from the role-oriented cultural paradigm of the Eiffel Tower in that the mission members are not pre-arranged. They must do whatever it takes to complete a task, and what to do is often ambiguous and may require a search.

The National Aerospace Agency (NASA) has pioneered the use of the project team to work in a space probe like a guided missile. To complete the moon landing mission requires 140 engineers from different fields. Their contributions are of vital importance especially at an unspecified time period. Since all engineers work in harmony with each other, to get the best combined results, the working process must be considered. No hierarchy can ever argue that "A's expertise is better than B". Everyone knows their work well. How do all members join the activity? All are equal, or at least almost equal because no one knows the contribution of others.

Such a team will need the leader or coordinator who is in charge of sub-assembly and the final stage. However, the general moderator may know less than experts in each industry and must respect them. These groups are egalitarian because they may need the help of any expert to change direction to achieve their goals. They may know the target but are uncertain about the direction. The rocket model is often appealing to professionals and has a cross discipline. For example, in an advertising agency, an ad writer, a designer, a media manager, a commercial filmmaker, and an account representative can work together in one battle. translate with customer consent. They all play the same role, however, what that role is depends on the final campaign preferred by the customer.

The rocket model is very expensive due to the hiring of specialists. Teams tend to work temporarily, relationships cease to bond when the project ends, and the means of implementation will stop working. Membership will join other project teams, with different purposes, lasting for a few days or weeks and possibly large numbers of members. This cultural model does not capture affection and devotion but is typical of a neutral culture.

The supreme human value in the rocket-driven culture model shows the way you work and the extent to which you contribute to the overall outcome. In fact, each team member shares it to solve the problem. The relative contribution of each individual may not be as obvious as in the Eiffel Tower model, where each role is clearly described and the outcome can be quantified.

b. Think, learn and change

The missile model guides the way in a targeted way, using feedback signals so it moves round, instead of translating. However, if the movement is translational, the missile also rarely changes its target. Therefore, the steering is accurate and durable, not geared toward new goals or potentials.

Learning includes "getting along with people", the ability to "break ice" quickly, taking on a missing role in the team, practicing more than theory, becoming a problem-solving center instead of a century center. the law. The assessment is usually given by an equal or a subordinate, not a superior.

The change occurred rapidly in the guided missile model. Goals are always moving, new goals appear, new working groups are formed, old groups disbanded. People moving from one group to another lead to greater job turnover trends than loyalty to the company. In many ways, the guided missile model contrasts with the family model with a long-lasting, lasting connection full of affection.

c. Encourage, reward and resolve conflicts

Encouragement gradually becomes essential in this culture. It is the members of the group who are always passionate, have a common goal and aim towards the end product. Apple Mancintosh, they were passionate about creating a "great machine". The work of this machine is an extraordinary achievement in which individual contradictions and animosity are set aside. Only broad participation has broad commitment. The consensus should only be in a large, though large scale to attract the participation of all people.

The rocket culture model tends to be personalization because it allows large numbers of experts from different disciplines to work together in a temporary facility. The work scene is always changing. Only the steadfast pursuit of personal development remains unchanged. The team shares passions among the members, but it is discarded and vanished when the work ends. The members are cheerful, have their own style and are smart, but they cooperate with each other for money, not for goals. They don't have to know each other too well and can avoid doing it.

3.4. Incubator culture model

The incubator culture model based on an organizational point of view is less important than individual perfection. If the organization is generous, they should be cradles for self-expression and self-improvement. The

goal is to free people from familiar ways, to become more creative, and to reduce time spent on self-sustaining lives. This model is personal and balanced.

a. Leadership, power and relationships among members

The incubator culture model serves as a healthy playground for generating ideas and responding intelligently to new ones. Typical examples are the new companies in Silicon Valley, California, Scotland; These are contractors, founded by a group of idea-rich people who abandoned their larger employer just before the payday. Becoming independent individuals, they are not bound by loyalty to the company and can develop themselves.

Incubator culture is not just about small innovation companies. They can be a group of practicing physicians, legal partners, some consultant, a qualified inspector or any group of specialists working almost independently but love sharing. share resources and experience. Some opinions suggest that the incubator model will be the organization model of the future.

Since the incubator model has a minimal structure, the hierarchy is also streamlined. Those in command are stern individuals, whose naturally exciting ideas and foresight inspiration have drawn others to work with them.

This cultural model often operates in a devoted emotional environment. However, in essence this conscientiousness is less directed towards people than towards the change of the world, considering the nature of social compensation.

The incubator model favors creativity and innovation. Due to close relationships, sharing extraordinary inspirations and goals, the model at its best can be honest, efficient, secure, and enjoyable, dependent on direct relationships and on sticking at work. Since this attachment is completely voluntary, nurtured and nurtured by hope and ideals, it can become the most valuable and meaningful experience in human life. The incubator model is characterized by the limitation of size due to the "scope of control" of the leader, because it is difficult to communicate naturally and comfortably with more than 75-100 people.

b. Thinking of learning and change

Changes in the incubator pattern can happen very quickly and quickly as the members get along very well. This is evident if you look at the jazz band's improvisation, the leader tries to come up with something new, the band will play along if they like it and skip it if they don't. All attendees have the same melody and emotion. But because the audience does not clearly define a specific goal, the problem is redefining and finding a common solution.

New American companies that follow the incubator model rarely achieve product and market perfection. The cultural paradigm learns to be creative, not how to survive when market demands change.

c. Encourage, reward and resolve conflicts

The words "70 hours a week and love it" on the T-shirt of Apple Computer Company used in the first days is the greatest encouragement for each individual. It takes a competition to contribute to forming something new. Everyone wants to have "control" in their hands. In addition to opening up the creative process, they also wanted a little bit of interest in personal safety, a little desire in terms of profitability and power. If successful, people will enjoy a lot of things. If not, the incubator model itself fails. Contrary to the family culture model, leadership in the incubator model is due to "obtained" rather than "attributed". You will follow the person with the workflow that impressed you the most and the person with the most feasible idea. The power to interfere with the collective achievement will be condemned. Conflict is resolved through division of jobs or trying to make others see which job is best.

4. Research on cultural models at Vinamilk

Vietnam has joined the international playing field, Vietnamese enterprises are facing great opportunities and challenges. Enterprises that want to create a solid position for themselves in this playground need to build their own ENTERPRISE CULTURE values with distinctive and appropriate identities. Vinamilk has done that. The company's culture has contributed to the success of the company it is today.

4.1. The tangible processes and structures of the enterprise

Vinamilk is the top famous dairy brand in Vietnam. That is why Vinamilk always puts quality on top. The image of Vinamilk's logo has shown that: the image of the company's name in the middle of the milky white color stands out in the cool green color as a sustainable commitment to the quality of Vinamilk. Along with the slogan: "International quality, Vinamilk quality". Not only the employees of the company have to pay attention, but surely the consumers of Vinamilk products also know by heart. Further affirming its image, Vinamilk's factories and factories are also associated with the two colors blue and white, located in a spacious, airy, clean campus that impresses employees and consumers. . Every employee working in factories must also dress clean and tidy. Everyone works with a friendly, enthusiastic and enthusiastic attitude. When coming to work, the employees are trained and guided enthusiastically about the qualifications as well as regulations and manners in the company. Here, people are also trained and heard stories about milk, nutrition ... like lessons and good traditions of the company. Every month, every year, the company always has festivals, summarizing the work to commend the achievements and draw experiences for its officers and employees. The company also organizes programs such as entertainment festivals, football tournaments throughout the company to tighten solidarity among members.

In addition, Vinamilk also regularly organizes charity fundraising activities such as: sponsoring competitions, glowing fireflies, hot air balloon 'with Vinamilk reaching to the sky', ... and private programs. customer health care consulting both connects employees and shows concern for public health.

In addition, Vinamilk's products are always available on the market with many types of products such as powdered milk, fresh milk, yogurt, coffee ..., diversifying models, expressing creativity and meeting demand. Diversified demand of customers of all sectors, all ages.

4.2. Declared Values

With the business philosophy: "Vinamilk wants to become the most popular product in all regions and territories. Therefore, we believe that quality and creativity are Vinamilk's companions. Vinamilk views customers as the center and commits to meeting all customers' needs. "And strategic vision:" vinamilk products with international quality always aim at the most perfect response to consumers ". Vinamilk has created for itself as well as each member a core value in spirit. In order to do that, each employee in the company can learn and set out for themselves the responsibility to strive for the mission and goals of Vinamilk.

"Vinamilk wants to become the most popular product in all regions and territories"

"The goal of the company is to continuously develop production, trade and service activities in business activities to maximize the profit possible of the company for shareholders, improve company value and continuously improving the lives, working conditions and incomes for employees, at the same time fulfilling the obligation to pay the State budget. Besides, Vinamilk connects the processing industry with the development of raw material areas in order to increase the independence of raw materials in the present and the future "

4.3. General notions

Vinamilk always puts quality on top, that is why each member of the company always immerses itself in Vinamilk's own culture: "Together, work together, do our best, quality is set. firstly, devoted to each product and all because of the desire to care for the community's health in the future next generation "

Each company, every business that wants to create a firm position in the marketplace needs to create a culture with its own identity. So is Vinamilk. As a well-known company for its dairy brands, Vinamilk has taken quality as the top quality in every member, in the company itself and in each product. Having a good tradition for the health of the community, the company's employees always show the spirit of mutual love and dedication to each product. That culture has contributed to creating a strong Vinamilk brand in the domestic and international markets.

5. Conclusion

Vietnamese ENTERPRISE CULTURE was formed as an important part of Vietnamese culture, which was handed down and further fostered in the current period of industrial excitement, modernization and active integration into the international economy. CORPORATE CULTURE Our country absorbs cultural factors in business that have been formed over the years of cultures around the world, and at the same time acquires and promotes cultural quintessence in the business of his father, The application is consistent with the characteristics of today's society, that is traditional modernization coupled with modernization. Only that way can a good combination of tradition and modernity, which is a combination of selective and enhanced, step by step forming ENTERPRISE CULTURE with Vietnamese identity.

Vietnam is a heroic country, having spent four thousand years building and defending the country. Vietnamese people are industrious and hard-working and have all the qualities of people who dare to face all challenges. With the results in study, labor and fighting has exuded a valuable thing that, although we Vietnamese people are small but very brave, intelligent and creative, this helps us to have enough confidence to recognize and help us build a firmer, more developed economy.

In such an environment, Vietnamese ENTERPRISE CULTURE also has many rich national identities. Moreover, Vietnamese businessmen have faced many difficulties brought about by war and backwardness, but in the "wisdom emerges", they show their creativity and resilience. Leadership has been trained in the challenge of "no arrogance, defeat without defiance". We have many working heroes in wartime as well as in peacetime. There are many typical examples for Vietnamese entrepreneurs such as Tran Ngoc Suong - Director of Hau River farm, Truong Gia Binh - General Director of Thang Long Joint Stock Company, Hoang Dinh Phi - Director of San Nam Co., Ltd. and many other typical examples, they are the people who have contributed to the face of the country's economy.

To get the current success, the leaders also have a powerful team of farm workers. Vietnamese working class is hard-working, honest and compassionate. In work as well as in life, we have great solidarity, saying as the late painter Trinh Cong Son wrote: "The ground is vast, brothers and sisters are one family". Always show mutual love, meaningful life. Vietnamese workers are not only faithful to their homeland, they are also very loyal to their ideals and organizations. A survey shows that the number of Vietnamese workers leaving the factory is very small, most of them persistently stick with their leaders and suffer with their leaders, there are almost no protests or strikes in agencies. factory in Vietnam.

Not only with the above qualities, Vietnamese workers are very intelligent and creative. They are the ones who bring in many innovations in production, many places where their intelligence helps businesses get out of difficulties and gain prestige in domestic and foreign markets. As Mr. Nguyen Cong Phu - General Director of Apave Vietnam and Southeast Asia Company, "Vietnamese people, who are more intelligent than anyone, do not know yet, but certainly not inferior to anyone"

We can be proud to acknowledge that there have been many changes and transformations of enterprises in adapting to changes in economics and science and technology since we opened the door until now. . Many companies have shifted from subsidy to self-accounting to operate very effectively and create jobs for many workers such as Vinamilk Dairy Company, Halida Beer Company ... many supermarkets. , the entertainment center quickly captures the tastes of customers and offers a modern operating model. Having the above

praiseworthy change, we must first mention the timely cultural change in enterprises. The result of cultural change is shown in many places, especially when we go to supermarkets and big factories, we encounter the atmosphere of working with modern industrial style with a team of skilled staff, Wear uniforms, speak politely. Many products are created with high quality, beautiful appearance, rich appearance and quality.

Due to long-term difficulties and wars, Vietnamese businesses have little opportunity to interact with the outside, so it can be said that although the adaptability of enterprises has many remarkable achievements, it is still very much slow. The investment in science and technology is still low, in many production places with outdated lines and machines due to lack of investment and investment funds. Concern for survival and out of poverty has always been haunted, so the future orientation is not paid much attention, such as the compulsory study of laws of countries before cooperating at many companies. Being overlooked, the branding before the goods was born is a fairly new concept for Vietnamese businessmen, which has cost us a lot of money and effort in the Pangasius lawsuit. brand Trung Nguyen coffee, fish sauce Phu Quoc or tobacco Vinataba are typical examples.

Employees at Vietnamese enterprises are trying very hard to gradually adapt to a new, very exciting life, but in general it is still very slow compared to some Asian countries such as Korea, Japan, China ... the work is still slow, especially in subsidized agencies. The working atmosphere is not really urgent, and in many places, employees have not absolutely complied with labor safety.

There are a number of foreigners who come to Vietnam to work very surprised because the working time in many enterprises is stretched, such as opening late, leaving early or appointments slower than planned. At many service establishments, although we encounter warm smiles and polite attitude, it is not enough without useful advice, sincere attitude and ability to provide accurate information about goods. chemical. Reflection "3C" - Laugh, Hi, Thank you are etched into the minds of employees in some places are still considered fake actions.

Due to the process of economic restructuring, many companies with multi-functions and multi-forms have emerged, contributing to the vitality of all economic sectors. In our country, most of them are small and medium companies, trying to assert the position and aim to develop the scale of operations. The overwhelming majority of small and private companies have advantages such as less administrative procedures, quick decision-making and the ability to capture the market quickly.

Talking about the benefits, we also have to discuss the harm. The ease of launching small companies and limited liability companies is also an opportunity for those with poor intellectuals, inexperienced management and business ethics to take control of leadership. Many companies have the look of nepotism, corporate culture is very weak, employees' rights are not guaranteed. There have been many companies operating in disguise, defrauding workers, evading taxes or taking into account profits without even a bit of conscience to the social community. Companies like EPCO Minh Phung and Thanh Huong fragrances are not uncommon until now.

It's not just the leadership in some ghost companies that is corrupt. In some water enterprises, moral degradation is also a common concern of the whole society. There are incompetent managers many years old due to the support should be classified in the leadership position.

The imposition of management is not a strange concept to us, not only during the subsidy period, but nowadays many places still maintain the type of leadership "above and below do not listen", many grim fate. , many talents are crushed by this type of management. In many businesses without the concept of "openness", all financial scandals, shady structural relationships are forever in eternal darkness.

It can also be said that many agencies lack knowledge is actually due to many young people not striving, sometimes they depend on dependence on staff, but in many places, the job placement is still based on bias, respect or acquaintance in the way "he lost his chicken leg, she stuck a bottle of wine". Among those recruited there is some fake knowledge by scholars, fake diplomas. A business will not be able to have a sustainable

cultural environment if only built with weak knowledge and an inertia to change. How damaging it would be if human resources management just had a reputation and wasn't real if we didn't consciously improve from today.

The assessment of staff capacity in many places is not good or confusing. The assessment without criteria or sometimes biased feelings also makes the subordinates depressed, the co-worker relationship is therefore worse, the working atmosphere is heavy, poor, and reputation with the leader is reduced.

Bonus policies in many businesses do quite well, the emulation atmosphere develops strongly, but there are also some places due to inaccurate assessment leading to inadequate reward policy, people with meritorious services. enjoy, and those who have no merit will be appreciated.

Rewarding, if it is just a formality, without content, is not only beneficial but also harmful. Many known people have complained that, at the office where they work, the awarding brings form disease and report on achievements, and in some places also has a policy of emulation to launch the movement and then leave it. There is a merit without a reward or just a disease of "beating the drumstick and getting rid of the stick".

Through the above view, it can be said that culture in many Vietnamese enterprises is still very weak. The causes for weakness can be drawn as follows:

- Many Vietnamese enterprises have not yet determined which business principle is important. Therefore, these businesses do not have clear operational goals and employee awareness is also very vague. The standard system of sustainable behavior has not yet been developed. The leadership team is uneven, many places are still poor.

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